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<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна

DSc. доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии N 3 СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Рашид Захидович

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<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>

Саидов Сандамир Аброрович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский фармацевтический институт
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

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Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии, неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергатовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Даминов Феруз Асадуллаевич

Декан лечебного факультета №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, доктор медицинских наук, доцент. Самарканд, Узбекистан.

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

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*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
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ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

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*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine, Tashkent
Medical Academy. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

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*PhD, Docent, Head of the Psychiatry Course at the Faculty of
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<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

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*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent Pediatric
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pediatric dermatovenerology and AIDS
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

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*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

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*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

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EGAMOVA Malika Tursunovna
PhD, assistant
Rasulov Jamshedlon Shavkat ugli
Samarkand State Medical University

EFFICACY OF FOLK REMEDIES IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS AT RISK OF STROKE

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ABSTRACT

Folk remedies are very effective and inexpensive methods and have recently come to be used in many areas of modern medicine. Of these methods, hirudotherapy is considered the most universal and effective. Hirudotherapy affects the rheological properties of deposits, leading to their liquefaction. We know that with ischemic stroke, the rheological properties of the blood are disrupted, which leads to its coagulation. This method results in improvement of the patient's condition.

Key words: effective treatment, continuous therapy, leech therapy, prevention of complications, defense mechanism.

ЭГАМОВА Малика Турсуновна
PhD

РАСУЛОВ Жамшеджон Шавкатович
Самаркандский Государственный Медицинский Университет

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ НАРОДНЫХ СРЕДСТВ У БОЛЬНЫХ САХАРНЫМ ДИАБЕТОМ С РИСКОМ ИНСУЛЬТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Народные средства являются весьма эффективными и недорогими методами и в последнее время стали применяться во многих областях современной медицины. Из этих методов наиболее универсальным и эффективным считается гирудотерапия. Гирудотерапия воздействует на реологические свойства отложений, приводя к их разжижению. Мы знаем, что при ишемическом инсульте нарушаются реологические свойства крови, что приводит к ее свертыванию. Этот метод приводит к улучшению состояния пациента.

Ключевые слова: эффективное лечение, непрерывная терапия, гирудотерапия, профилактика осложнений, защитный механизм.

EGAMOVA Malika Tursunovna

PhD

RASULOV Jamshedjon Shavkatovich

Samarkand Davlat tibbiyot universiteti

ISHEMIK INSULT XAVFI BO'LGAN QANDLI DIABET BEMORLAR UCHUN XALQ TABOBATI USULLARIDA DAVOLANISHINING SAMARADORLIGI

ANNOTATSIYA

Xalq tabobati juda samarali va arzon usullar bo'lib, yaqinda ular zamonaviy tibbiyotning ko'plab sohalarida qo'llanila boshlandi. Ushbu usullardan hirudoterapiya eng universal va samarali hisoblanadi. Hirudoterapiya qonning reologik xususiyatlariga tayanadi, bu ularning suyuqlanishiga olib keladi. Biz bilamizki, ishemik insult paytida qonning reologik xususiyatlari buziladi, bu uning ivishiga olib keladi. Bu usul bemorni axvoli ijobiy tomonga o'zgarishiga olib keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: samarali davolash, doimiy terapiya, hirudoterapiya, operatsiyalarning oldini olish, harakat mexanizmi.

The use of folk remedies in modern medicine is considered a very cheap and effective method for patients and doctors. Given the effective action of hirudotherapy in diabetes and stroke, the mechanism of its action in these diseases has been studied. [1; 5; 11; 14].

Diabetes mellitus, also known as sugar diabetes, is a disease caused by insulin deficiency and metabolic disorders in the body. Diabetes has been known in Eastern folk medicine for a long time. Abu Ali ibn Sina pays special attention to this disease. "Water comes out the same as it was drunk," he writes. Excessive consumption of water by the patient also causes other diseases, and the patient loses a lot of weight. Dwelling on the procedures, the doctor says: "Give the patient cold liquids to drink, pour them into a cold bowl, drink sour ayran, give fruits and drink mint tea, in other words, maintain the water balance and coolness of the patient." This means that the disease occurs due to an increase in body temperature. According to historical medical sources, diabetes can also be a hereditary disease. In diabetes, blood sugar levels rise sharply and are excreted in urine, leading to symptoms such as thirst, weight loss, weakness, itching, and others. [1; 16].

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a disease characterized by insufficient insulin production in the body or loss of cell sensitivity to it, which leads not only to an increase in glucose levels in the body, but also damages the cardiovascular system. In patients with CT, blood rheology changes, which leads to its thickening, slowing down of blood circulation and simultaneously increasing the risk of ischemic stroke. Ischemic stroke is a disease caused by a violation of the blood supply to the brain, leading to the death or serious damage of nerve cells. In diabetes mellitus, the rheological properties of the blood change, that is, its viscosity, aggregation of red blood cells in the blood, and the tendency to thrombosis. These changes lead to a slowdown in blood circulation, damage to microvessels and severe pathologies of the cardiovascular system. Therefore, effective treatment of diabetes plays an important role in reducing its impact on blood rheology and preventing the risk of ischemic stroke. The article discusses changes in blood rheology in diabetes mellitus, their impact on the development of ischemic stroke, and the positive effect of hirudotherapy on blood rheology. In diabetes mellitus, blood rheology changes mainly under the influence of several factors. The most important of these are blood viscosity, the tendency to thrombus formation, and circulatory disorders. In diabetes, blood viscosity increases, which complicates its movement through the vessels and increases the risk of blockage of microvessels. The tendency to thrombus formation also increases, since the number of platelets in the blood increases and their activity increases. This condition leads to blood clotting and contributes to the occurrence of ischemic stroke. In addition, in diabetes, common conditions are slow blood circulation, decreased vascular elasticity, and damage to microvessels. These conditions not only lead to the spread of insulin throughout the body, but also impair the functioning of the entire cardiovascular system.

Hirudotherapy, or leech therapy, is a medical practice that has been used since ancient times and is considered an effective means of reducing blood clotting and improving circulation. Hirudotherapy reduces blood viscosity and the tendency to thrombosis, normalizes blood circulation and improves microvascular blood flow. This method helps improve the rheological properties of the blood and reduce the risk of ischemic stroke, especially in patients with diabetes. [3; 10; 17].

Hirudotherapy improves blood circulation by reducing blood clotting. Leech saliva contains a substance called hirudin, which inhibits thrombin activity and stops the blood clotting process. This reduces platelet aggregation and thrombus formation processes, which ensures normal blood circulation. At the same time, hirudotherapy reduces blood viscosity, reducing the risk of microvascular occlusion. [1].

Another positive effect of hirudotherapy is the restoration of microvascular blood flow by improving blood circulation. Due to impaired microcirculation in diabetes, the blood supply to various organs and tissues is difficult. Hirudotherapy improves this process and helps normalize microvascular blood flow. This, in turn, helps reduce the risk of stroke. Hirudotherapy also has an antiplatelet and anticoagulant effect, which makes it an effective tool for managing platelets and the blood coagulation system. Reducing blood clotting helps prevent microvascular blockage, promotes normal blood flow and ensures the smooth functioning of blood vessels. [2; 714; 4].

In addition, hirudotherapy helps improve the overall health of patients with diabetes by reducing high blood pressure, blood clotting factors and damage to microvessels. Hirudotherapy not only normalizes the rheological properties of the blood, but also increases the elasticity of blood vessels, promotes full restoration of blood circulation. Thus, hirudotherapy can be an effective means of preventing ischemic stroke in patients with diabetes.

The role of blood rheology in the development of ischemic stroke in diabetes: Changes in blood rheology in diabetes are mainly associated with the following factors:

1. Blood viscosity: With diabetes, blood viscosity increases, which makes it difficult for blood to move through the vessels. Increased viscosity leads to blockage of microvessels, which, in turn, increases the risk of ischemic stroke.

2. Tendency to thrombosis: in patients with diabetes, the blood coagulation system is disrupted, the number of platelets in the blood plasma increases, and the level of thrombin increases. This causes blood to clot and can cause ischemic stroke.

3. Circulatory problems: In diabetes, high blood pressure and blood thickening factors impair microvascular circulation, causing problems with adequate insulin delivery.

4. Microvascular damage: CT, especially if left unmonitored for a long time, causes microvascular damage to the arteries. As a result, the vessels become less elastic, blood circulation deteriorates, and the risk of ischemic stroke increases. [6; 5; 9; 10].

Therefore, to prevent ischemic stroke in diabetes, it is necessary to improve the rheological properties of the blood and restore its normal properties.

The effect of hirudotherapy on blood rheology: Hirudotherapy, or leech therapy, is a medical practice that has been used since ancient times. This method is considered an effective means of reducing blood clotting and improving blood circulation. Hirudotherapy helps improve blood rheology in the following ways:

1. Reduces blood clotting: leech saliva, due to its unique biochemical composition, blocks the blood's ability to clot and prevents blood clots. This method ensures normal blood circulation and reduces the risk of ischemic stroke.

2. Reduces blood clotting: hirudotherapy helps reduce blood viscosity, which promotes its proper and effective circulation. As a result, blood flow in microvessels slows down and becomes less clogged.

3. Antiplatelet and anticoagulant effect: Hirudotherapy has an antiplatelet and anticoagulant effect, suppressing platelet aggregation and thrombin activity. This plays an important role in the prevention of ischemic stroke, stopping blood clotting and reducing vascular occlusion.

4. Improves blood circulation: hirudotherapy normalizes blood circulation by increasing blood permeability and improving microcirculation, which improves overall well-being and reduces the risk of ischemic stroke.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it can be said that the use of hirudotherapy in diabetes mellitus and ischemic stroke has proven itself to be a very effective method. Changes in blood rheology in diabetes mellitus and their important role in the development of ischemic stroke are shown. Hirudotherapy can be effective in reducing the risk of ischemic stroke by reducing blood clotting, reducing viscosity and improving blood circulation. This method is important as an additional treatment for patients with diabetes mellitus. The article also presents the potential of hirudotherapy in the treatment of diabetes and the prevention of ischemic stroke.

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